

INFLUENCE OF SiC PARTICLES VOLUME FRACTION ON DUCTILE DAMAGE PROCESS IN AL-Si METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: It is well known that composites are, in most of the cases, notch insensitive and traditional fracture mechanics concepts, as stress intensity factor, are inadequate to describe material performance. In addition to the complex damage state that takes place in composite materials, metal matrix composites (MMC) present an additional damage process as a result of plastic deformations. One of the basic microstructural process for ductile damage is the formation and growth of cavities in the ductile matrix when irreversible strains take place as a result of the external loading. In particulate composites this process is emphasized by the presence of the brittle particles deep drowned in the matrix where voids are initiated as a result of matrix-particle debonding. In this paper, ductile damage evolution was measured on two Aluminum based MMC characterized by different SiC particles volume fractions. Several experimental tests shown that even if failure strain is very low, plasticity takes place in the material microstructure. Once the ductile matrix is yielded, the included particles debonds acting as microvoids initiators. As result of this process, damage evolution law come out to be very steep.

KEYWORDS: damage, mechanics, microvoids, Al-Li/SiC composites

INTRODUCTION

Linear elastic regime in metal matrix composites (MMC) is characterized by a very low strain range. For instance, Newaz and Majumdar [1] and Brust et alii [2] observed that elastic range in SCS-6/Ti-15-3 MMC is below 0.0035 strain for unidirectional composite and below 0.002 strain for 90° oriented laminate. Non-linearities observed in the stress-strain curve for higher strain levels is the results of two processes: the first, is the plastic deformation that takes place in the ductile matrix; the latter, is the appearance of damage process as a result of the debond between the matrix and the included brittle particles or fibers.

In the present paper the attention is focused on two aluminum-silicium based composites reinforced with 10% and 20% SiC dispersed particles, respectively. Even if the presence of the included SiC particles increases the material stiffness, on the other hand it seems to reduce dramatically the strain to failure.

Experimental observation shows that the bond between the matrix and the included brittle particles is mainly due to the gripping effect of the matrix produced during the cooling down phase of the manufacturing process, (Bonora et alii, [3]). As a consequence of this, SiC particles play the role of microvoids initiators that nucleate under monotonic straining.

Even if, several continuum damage mechanics models that describe the effect of void growth in ductile metals are available (Lemaitre, [4], Chow and Wang, [5], Gurson, [6]), very few of them take into account of the non linear behavior of damage evolution as a function of imposed strain. Recently, Bonora [7],[8] presented a non-linear damage model based on the nucleation, steady growth and coalescence process of microvoids in a ductile matrix.

According to Bonora [7], damage evolution can be given by the following equation,

$$dD = \alpha \cdot \frac{(D_{cr} - D_0)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}{\ln(\epsilon_{cr}) - \ln(\epsilon_{th})} \cdot f\left(\frac{\sigma_H}{\sigma_{eq}}\right) \cdot (D_{cr} - D)^{\frac{\alpha-1}{\alpha}} \cdot \frac{dp}{p} \quad (1)$$

where p is the effective plastic strain, D_0 and D_{cr} are the initial and the critical damage; ϵ_{th} and ϵ_{cr} are the threshold strain for which damage processes are initiated and the critical strain to failure; $f(\sigma_H/\sigma_{eq})$ is a function that takes into account of the triaxial state of stress where σ_H is hydrostatic stress and σ_{eq} is the equivalent Mises stress. α is the damage exponent that characterizes the damage evolution law for the material under investigation.

This equation, together with the elastic and plastic equations gives a rational description for the constitutive model of a ductile metal damaged by microvoids growth.

This model comes out also to be able to describe the material response of those ductile metals where the presence of damage, as a result of large included particles, induces brittle fracture. For instance, failure in Al-Li 2091 alloy resulted to be due to the concurrent actions of two-steps process. Initially, plastic deformation takes place in the material in form of narrow slip bands where included particles nucleate microvoids, (Bonora et alii, [3]). Once the plastic deformed region is saturated by nucleated voids, the further increase of the imposed strain induces a sudden linking of the nucleated cavities through cleavage cracks with consequent failure of the material, as shown in Fig.1. This kind of process resulted to be characterized by a well defined damage curve as depicted in Fig.2. Similar damage curve was observed by Chow and Wang [5] on Al 7075 alloy.

Fig. 1: Cleavage initiating from microvoid in Al-Li, from Bonora et alii, [10]

In both cases, the Bonora's model was able to predict particularly well the experimental data. In this paper, the damage evolution in Al-Si alloy reinforced with SiC particles was studied integrating damage measurements, obtained in form of loss of stiffness, with microstructural observations using electron scanning microscope.

Two were the issues addressed in this work: the understanding of the global material response using a damage description that takes into account of the irreversible deformation process that occurs in the microstructure prior failure and the effect of a different particles content on the damage evolution law.

Fig. 2: Damage variable evolution in Al2024.

MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material under investigation is a Al-Si/SiC composite produced by injection of SiC particles during the pressure die casting process in form of tiles with dimensions: $140 \times 140 \times 12.7$ mm. Zenisek et alii. [9] observed that the mean SiC particle areas $70 \mu\text{m}^2$ for the 10% composites and $100 \mu\text{m}^2$ for the 20%, approximately. A sample of the microstructure is given in Fig. 3a-3b where the back scatter electron image highlights the SiC particles shape and content.

From each tile with 10% and 20% SiC content, at least 10 specimens were obtained and tested. For the specimen geometry, the rectangular strip configuration was chosen. Initially, an hourglass-shape geometry, as proposed by Bonora et alii [10], was used in order to localize the damage process in the pre-defined section instrumented with small strain gauges. Unluckily, this configuration resulted to be not useful as a result of the very low strain at failure of the material that reduced the possibility to control the deformation process and damage acquisition. A more general specimen geometry, as used by Chow and Wang [5], was

used. In this case, no section reduction was performed and damage was monitored, and averaged, on a length of 25 mm. In Fig. 4 the specimen dimensions are given.

Back scatter electron image highlights the SiC particles shape and content in 10 and 20% SiC composites, respectively.

Fig. 4: Specimen geometry and dimensions.

Each specimen was cut with electroerosion machine in order to avoid a too deep material hardening and to obtain a cleaner surface cut. Specimen surfaces were polished to rectify defects caused by the impression or detachment of SiC into or out from the matrix.

For each composites, traction tests were performed both in strain and load control. The results obtained were extremely close indicating a very low scatter in the stress-strain material curve. In Fig. 5, the stress-strain curves obtained with several specimens is plotted for a 20% and 10% SiC particles content.

Fig. 5: Stress-strain curves for 10% and 20% Al-Si/SiC composite.

Damage was measured using instant Young's modulus measurements. The instant stiffness is normalized by the reference modulus measured in the very early linear part of the stress-strain curve.

Alternatively, damage measurement using multiple unloading technique has been also performed. Both techniques gave similar damage estimations.

Fig. 6: Damage evolution in 20% Al-Si/SiC composite.

In Fig. 6, the damage curves for the 20% SiC composites are given. Damage cumulates rapidly, almost linearly, with strain. This kind of behavior, for which below a given threshold

strain no damage is produced and as soon as this strain value is exceeded a large amount of damage is generated, is typical of brittle materials. Similarly to Al-Li alloy, here plasticity is localized. In the plastic zone, particles rapidly debond from the matrix reducing the effective net resisting section with a highly localized loss of stiffness that soon induces material failure.

The scanning electron microscope (SEM) analysis revealed that failure process in 10% SiC composite initiates at SiC particle boundary where plastic deformation occurs. If the strain field is strong enough, the particle can be ripped away. When the particle is fully debonded from the matrix, cleavage occurs. In Fig. 7a close up of the fracture surface is given. This picture shows how, after particle debond as a result of plastic deformation, cleavage fracture proceeds through the Aluminum-Si matrix.

In 20% SiC composite failure process maintains the same basic characteristic as illustrated above. However, this multiple sites induced tearing is increased as a result of the higher particles content but cleavage process is arrested by the presence of the neighborhood particles. Thus, failure surfaces results in a completely different morphology, as showed in Fig. 7b, that can explain the higher strain at failure observed macroscopically and the higher value of the critical damage.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the damage mechanisms in Al-Si composite reinforced with two different SiC particle contents has been investigated.

The presence of the particle reinforcement resulted in a higher material performance in terms of stiffness and strength respect to the base matrix metal. However, this increase of stiffness is accompanied by an highly reduced strain to failure that strongly reduces the material applicability.

The present study highlighted the role of damage mechanisms that takes place in the material under straining. More particularly, the experimental tests performed showed that damage mechanisms are activated as soon as the strain is applied. In this direction, damage measurements indicate that damage process starts for strain higher then 0.0005 mm/mm.

The effect of the particles content strongly affects material failure. In the case of 10% SiC composite, particles performs as a initiation nuclei that trigger cleavage as soon as the particles are debonded by plastic deformation. When the particles content is higher, the same particles has the double action to initiate cleavage and to arrest it. This process results in a higher material damage tolerance, even if strain at failure remains very low.

In order to measure damage using a continuum damage mechanics, the non linear damage model proposed by Bonora has been used and the material damage parameters have been identified. Once again the non linear damage law, as proposed by Bonora, resulted to be able to follows completely the damage evolution in this material.

Fig. 7a: Fracture mechanism in 10% Al-Si/SiC composite: close up near a ripped SiC particle surrounded by extended cleavage areas.

Fig. 7b: Close up of the fracture surface in 20% Al-Si/SiC composite.

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